

INFLUENCE OF LIBRARY RESOURCES UTILIZATION ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN PUBLIC POLYTECHNICS IN BENUE STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The paper investigated the influence of library resources utilization on academic performance of students in public polytechnics in Benue State. Specifically, the study sought to: identify the library resources, examine the influence of library resources on academic performance of students and find out whether the students are satisfied with the library resources provided. Three research questions were raised in line with the purposes of the study to guide the research. The paper adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of four (4) public polytechnics in the Benue state with a 9437 students. The sample size for the study was 370 students derived using random sampling. Questionnaire was used to collect data while data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research. Results revealed that, library resources such as monographs/textbooks, card catalogue, online public access catalogue, e-books, newspapers, journals, e-databases such as AGORA, EBSCOhost, JSTOR etc, CD-ROM and library staff are provided by the polytechnic libraries. The study also found that library resources have significant influence on academic performance of students in areas such as; improving their readings skills, helping them to pass their examination with high grades, making them participate in academic discourse among others and finally, the level of satisfaction from the library resources provided to the students was low. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among other that: the management of the Polytechnics Libraries should be more proactive in the area of awareness of information resources in the library by showing them the benefits they could derive from using them through various means including, flyers, user education programs need to be revolutionised, modern ICT equipment should be factor in, including practical instructions to ensure adequate understanding of library activities by users. By this, students will be well oriented about the activities of the library and how to access, retrieve and use the available information resources on their own effectively.

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Introduction

Academic libraries are the ones established and maintained by higher institutions of learning such as universities, polytechnics, colleges of education, and schools of nursing, petroleum training institutes and schools of health technology. The essence of establishing an academic library is to enable it support the curriculum of the tertiary institutions which established it (Uwaifo, 2010). They are essential part of the learning community. It is a central service or unit of operation set up to provide location of materials and facilities for study, teaching and research carried out in the institution. The main function of an academic library is to serve as an auxiliary to the parent institution in carrying out its objectives. The Library is an important intellectual resource of the academic community, and helps them fulfill the curriculum requirements and to promote studies and research (Rajendran & Rathinasabapathy, 2005). The library caters for the information needs of the community, through the provision of reading materials for the various programmes of the institution.

According to Danton (2013), the major obligation of the academic library with respect to its book selection and book collection is to provide the materials which will now and in the future best contribute to the fulfillment of these closely related functions of teaching, conservation and research. Ajibero (2005) opined that the academic library is the “heart” of the institution. He contends that what all academic libraries have in common, virtually regardless of country or history is their basic position, roles, aims and objectives. The reputation of libraries depends highly on the library facilities it offers its clientele in terms of information resources. As information and research resources become more varied, it places a challenge on academic libraries. Karl (2014) asserted that a library with well organised facilities encourages the users to locate and borrow physically available library resources.

Iwhihwu and Okorodudu (2012) viewed library resources to mean anything that can provide intellectual stimulation to the reader and it includes periodicals, newspapers, pamphlets, ephemera, audio materials, film materials and computers as well as individuals in the community. Information resources are all library materials including books, electronic books, grey literatures, thesis and dissertations, statistical reports, manuscripts, government publications, journals, audio e-books, DVDs, Blu- rays console games, print and non- print materials) (Medway Libraries & Archives, 2012). Library resources are therefore stock in trade of library, they are the materials which the users come to consult, read or borrow. Information resources are many and they also vary, but can be divided into two broad categories; printed and non-printed materials. The majority of academic libraries collect a variety of materials which include not only traditional print-on-paper media like books, journals, newspapers and maps, but also audio visuals, CD-ROMS, computer software, online databases, internet, e-books, e-journals and other media (Halsey as cited in Agbo, 2014).

Going by the above, it is evident that academic libraries help to accelerate the implementation of educational programmes so that the aims and objectives of education could be achieved (Arinde, 2010; Owata & Iroha, 2013). According to the World Bank (2008), availability of functional academic library provides additional reading opportunities for students, thus improve their knowledge, writing skills, reading skills and clarity of expression leading to their academic performance. Fakomogbon (2012) opined that since curriculum is dynamic, academic library help to support both students and teachers in school because it keep them abreast of new development in education and helps students carry out their academic activities thereby enhancing their academic performance.

Academic performance according to Nalah (2014) is the outcome of educational goals that are achieved either by students or the teacher. That is, how well a student meets standards set out by local authority or institution itself. Academic performance represents outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished

specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environment specifically in school, college and university. School systems mostly define cognitive goals that either apply across multiple subject areas (e.g. critical thinking) or include the acquisition of knowledge and understanding in a specific intellectual domain (e.g. numeracy, literacy, science and history). Therefore, academic performance should be considered to be a multifaceted construct that comprises different domains of learning. The polytechnic library therefore is a pivotal aspect of the institutions that helps students carry out their academic activities as such should be provided with quality library resources that are current and up-to-date in the different fields to enable the students make the best of it to perform academically well. It is against this backdrop that this study sought to investigate the influence of library resources utilization on academic performance of students in public polytechnics in Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

Polytechnic libraries occupy a vital position in the provision and dissemination of information to the academic community. They keep the academic community abreast of the current trend in their areas of research through the provision and dissemination of meaningful information resources. Access and use of these resources will enable students to develop their social and academic potentials as well as capabilities.

Students who may not be making use of these resources may stand the risk of lacking the necessary skills and intellectual development which will also result to failure in their examination and assignments, consequently leading to low performances in their grades which may cause some to be withdrawn for not meeting the stipulated CGPA and some not graduating. This is because it may lead them to not been aware of the available and enough literature in their areas to complement or support their lectures or classroom activities.

In view of the value of library and information resources, polytechnic libraries are heavily investing in the acquisition of print and non print information resources in a bid to supporting quality teaching, learning and research. However, while the libraries acquire and manage these resources for use, students may not know the influence of the resources on their academic performance and may not be making use of the libraries and their information resources leading to failure in their examinations, inability to writer their term papers, assignments and write their projects which could result to poor performances in their academics. It is against this backdrop that this paper investigated influence of library resources utilization on academic performance of students in public polytechnics in Benue State to know the level of students' preparedness and awareness of the library resources in their library.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of library resources utilization on academic performance of students in public polytechnics in Benue State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Identify the library resources provided in the polytechnic libraries under study.
- ii. Examine the influence of library resources on academic performance of students in the polytechnic libraries under study.
- iii. find out whether the students are satisfied with the library resources provided by the polytechnic libraries under study

Research Questions

- i. What are the library resources provided in the polytechnic libraries under study?
- ii. What is the influence of library resources on academic performance of students in the polytechnic libraries under study?
- iii. Are the students satisfied with the library resources provided in the polytechnic libraries under study?

Literature Review

Academic libraries are fundamental part of tertiary institutions, they assist in improving learning and dissemination of knowledge so as to meet the information needs of the universities and their communities through the provision of timely information. The backbone of teaching, learning and research in any discipline is information resources (Maxwell, 2018).

Ezenwa as cited in Joy & Lucky (2016) stated that library resources are collection of wide variety of educational media which include books, magazines, newspapers and pamphlets, records and tapes, maps, films, photographs and painting. He added that library resources consist of both print and non-print media, like books, periodicals newspaper, pamphlets, brochure, ephemerals, photographs, slides, audiotapes, filmstrips, motion films, video tapes, computer diskettes and realia which are organized to broaden reading and the learning horizon of students and other library users. Dike as cited in cited in Joy & Lucky (2016) grouped library resources into three basic categories:

- a. Non-fiction print media
- b. Literature
- c. Audio visual resources

The first category is perhaps the most diverse and includes: reference materials, general non-fiction, periodicals and vertical file materials. Dike explains that literature is the major component of the library collection which includes books, pictures and fiction. The third category is the audio-visual resources which do not depend solely on reading to convey meaning. They include records, tapes and cassettes, radio, real objects, three dimensional displays, etc.

Moreso, Popoola and Haliso in Buhari (2016) further stressed that for an academic library to be effective, it must have enough information resources and sufficiently well trained information professionals. Information resources are regarded as information bearing materials that exists in printed and electronic formats, such as journals, textbooks, abstracts, indexes, magazines, newspapers, reports, diskettes magnetic disk, the internet/Email, video, CD-ROM databases, microforms, computers, and so on (Popoola and Haliso cited in Okiki (2013). Therefore, information resources are print, non-print as well as electronic materials that can be accessed either manually or electronically by library users. User's information needs can be met by a library through acquiring, organising and making accessible relevant information resources with the aid of appropriate facilities.

It is expected that undergraduate students utilise information resources in the library to meet all their information needs and for academic excellence. There is positive correlation between undergraduate academic attainment and the use of a variety of library resources and services such as using the catalogue, obtaining assistance from library personnel and using different information resources such as journal articles, electronic resources, books and reference works. In lieu of this, Adetimirin and Idowu (2014) further stressed that undergraduates are expected to study further after class instructions in order to collect relevant information for their class assignments, seminars, term papers, dissertations, theses and projects. All these can be done through the use of library and its information resources.

According to Ilori (2019) academic library plays essential role in every institution, by offering services to undergraduate students, researchers and other users. Academic libraries' role is to provide and maintain standard intellectual resources that will stimulate users' interest in promoting and adding value to such institution (Onyekweodiri and Agbo (2015).

The importance of libraries and its resources to education generally lies in the fact that they provide necessary information to lecturers, students and researchers and community services. The significance of academic

libraries lies in the fact that they are repositories of knowledge that provide the vital underpinning for national development (Alokun, 2003). Libraries also exist as dynamic instruments of education to enable their parent institutions discharge their teaching and research functions. Libraries are important because they are store-houses of information or record of human experience to which researchers can turn for information. Such libraries make available and accessible to their clientele information resources needed for research.

Therefore, a library with a current and organised library resources allow students and users to easily access and retrieve information resources from the shelves for learning, research and writing of terms papers which results to improvement in their academic performance. However, when library resources are wrongly shelved or improperly shelved, it becomes tedious and time consuming for users to access and retrieve information materials on the shelf. This is supported by Popoola & Haliso (2012) who observed that information availability does not mean accessibility and use and that academic libraries should stimulate primary demand for their products and services. This view is further upheld by Mason (2010), who opined that librarians must be sympathetic and helpful to all students on the one hand, and on the other hand, students must be aware that librarians and faculty members are there to instruct and encourage their intellectual odyssey and should be seen as facilitators.

Availability of library information resources has great influence on library use. Ilori (2019) opined that availability is the most important determinant of the extent to which information resources is used compared to all other factors, it is what is available that will be organised for easy access, awareness and use. Chiedu (2014) further stressed that library resources as well as physical infrastructure and facilities must be made available and adequate to achieve internal quality assurance whose ultimate goal is for the polytechnic to meet requisite standards while striving towards its goal. Chiedu (2014) In Agbetuyi et al therefore, posited that for a polytechnic to be able to carry out its tripartite mandate of teaching, research and community development (service), certain elements that contribute to the existence of the university must be present in adequate qualitative and quantitative measure. Therefore, library must be stocked with current books and journals in hard and soft (electronic) copies to enrich the knowledge of the teacher/ researcher and learners, thus motivating them to generate knowledge that will further update knowledge.

Findings of a study carried out by Jamogha, Jamogha and Godwin (2019) on “influence of ICT skills on library information resources utilisation by undergraduates” showed that the level of library information resources use by undergraduates was low except that monographs/textbooks and reference materials were highly used. In a study carried out by Onifade, Ogbuiyi and Omeluzor (2013) on library resources and service use by postgraduate students in a Nigerian private university, based on the result, it was ascertained that postgraduate students do not maximise the use of library resources provided for them because majority of them do not use the library on a regular basis. They preferred internet sources to print resource, lack of time on their part was the major problem.

Many scholars have studied use of library and information resources in higher institutions. In a study by Oluwatobi, Ehioghae, Aluko-Arowolo and Onasote (2014) on “the utilisation of library resources for effective research output among postgraduate students in Adventist University of Africa”, respondents affirmed that the available information resources in the library have a very low impact on their respective research work. Similarly, in a another study conducted by Mani, Vijayalakshmi, Thirumagal, and Priyadharshini (2019) on the usage of e-resources among the students of Manonmaniam Sundaranar University (MSU), Tirunelveli, the result of the study shows that 78.3% of the respondents are aware and utilised e-resources, 63% are using e-resources in the frequency of 2-3 times in a week, 53% are using e-resources for research purpose, 59% are accessing e-resources in the library, 17.3% are using e-resources to improve professional competence, 39% of the respondents felt that lack of training as a key constraint for the effective use of e-resources and 35% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the present e-collection of the library. They concluded in their study that Library plays important role in the usage of e-resources by its users and suggested that Library should facilitate e-resources by giving training for the effective usage of e-resources by the users.

Olorunfemi & Ipadeola (2011) averred that availability of relevant information resources, proper organisation of the resources, its awareness through various means such as user education and utilisation of information

resources are factors that ensure user's satisfaction. Relentless promotional and marketing efforts are critical by libraries to ensure maximum and efficient use of information resources by users. Expectations of libraries are achieved when information resources are fully utilised. Therefore, carrying out consistent appraisals on user needs and satisfaction regularly on various aspects of library usage will be a helpful guide for librarians in library planning to keep meeting with the library goals and objectives.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is a descriptive survey research design. Emaikwu (2013) defined a descriptive survey as the type of research design that describes in a systematic manner the characteristics, features or facts about a given population. The area of study is Benue State Nigeria. Benue state is located in the North-Central geo-political zone of Nigeria. It is made up of 23 local government areas and 3 senatorial zones namely; Benue North West, Benue North East and Benue South West. Benue state is majorly an agrarian state. The population of the study consisted of four (4) public polytechnics in the state namely, Federal Polytechnic Wannune, Alfred Akawe Torkula Polytechnic, Makurdi, College of Akperan Orshi College of Agriculture Yandev, and Benue State Polytechnic Ugbokolo. Data available by the office of academic planning of the institutions revealed that; Federal Polytechnic Wannune has 110 students, Alfred Akawe Torkula Makurdi has 92 students College of Agriculture Yandev has 4235 while Benue State Polytechnic Ugbokolo has 5000 students totalling 9437 (Source: Academic Records of FPW, AOCAY, AKTPM and Benpoly Ugbokolo). The sample size for the study was 370 students derived using random sampling. Random sampling gives each member of the population equal chance to participate. The choice of random sampling technique was to enable the researcher to have equal right of randomly making a uniform selection from all participants. Questionnaire was the instrument for data collection. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions, therefore, any item with a cut off value of 2.50 and above were agreed while those below 2.50 were disagreed. Chi-square (χ^2) of goodness of fit was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was, if the calculated probability value is greater than the set alpha value of 0.05, the null hypotheses was not rejected but if it is less, it was rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the library resources provided in the polytechnic libraries under study?

Table 1: Library resources provided in the polytechnic libraries under study.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Remark	
	Library resources provided								
1	Monographs/textbooks	130	179	41	20	3.13	0.81	Agreed	
2	Card catalogue	56	169	137	8	2.74	0.74	Agreed	
3	Online Public Access Catalogue	68	146	136	20	2.71	0.83	Agreed	
4	E-books	52	154	120	44	2.58	0.88	Agreed	
5	Newspapers	157	180	17	16	3.29	0.75	Agreed	
6	Journals	78	128	124	40	2.66	0.93	Agreed	
7	E-databases like Ebscohost, AGORA, JSTOR and BioOne,	52	153	121	44	2.58	0.88	Agreed	
8	Projects, thesis and dissertations	122	196	20	32	3.10	0.85	Agreed	
9	CD-ROM	69	201	72	28	2.84	0.81	Agreed	
10	Library staff	60	146	108	56	2.57	0.94	Agreed	

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table1 above sought to identify library resources provided in the polytechnic libraries under study. Result showed that all the items were above the cut-off point of 2.50. Library resources provided in the libraries were monographs/textbooks, card catalogue, online public access catalogue, e-books, newspapers, journals, e-databases such as AGORA, EBSCOhost, JSTOR etc, CD-ROM and library staff with all the items scoring above 2.50 which indicates the respondents agreed that, all the library resources are provided in libraries under study.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of library resources on academic performance of students in the polytechnic libraries under study?

Table 2: Influence of library resources on academic performance of students in the polytechnic libraries under study

S/N	Item Description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1	Improvement in reading skills	182	156	12	20	3.35	0.79	Agreed
2	Distraction of academic activities	57	154	79	80	2.51	1.00	Agreed
3	Promotion of computer skills	172	158	16	24	3.29	0.87	Agreed
4	Independent reading study habits	136	146	68	20	3.08	0.87	Agreed
5	Reduces my reading interest	53	146	75	96	2.42	1.3	Disagreed
6	Enabling students to pass examination with good grades.	170	164	4	32	3.26	0.86	Agreed
7	Contribute more on academic issue in group discussion enhancing comprehension	125	189	28	28	3.11	0.84	Agreed
8	Interacting with other students on-line on academic issues	136	186	20	28	3.16	0.84	Agreed
9	Assisting students with current literature for review	164	146	48	12	3.25	0.80	Agreed
10	Influencing students performance in seminar writing and presentation	116	174	60	20	3.04	0.83	Agreed
11	Passing examinations	132	185	25	28	3.14	0.84	Agreed

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 2 examined the influence of library resources on academic performance of students in the polytechnic libraries under study. Result indicated that the respondents agreed to all the items except for item 5 which they disagreed that it didn't reduce their reading habits which scored below 2.50. This shows that respondents in the study area agreed that the use of library resources have influence on their academic performance.

Research Question 3: Are the students satisfied with the library resources provided in the polytechnic libraries under study?

Table 3: Students satisfaction with library resources provided in the polytechnic libraries under study

S/N	Item description	VHS	HS	S	NS	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
	Level of satisfaction							
1	Monographs/textbooks	169	88	49	64	2.98	1.13	Satisfied
2	Card catalogue	163	69	66	72	2.87	1.18	Satisfied
3	Online Public Access Catalogue	86	96	120	68	2.54	1.05	Satisfied
4	E-books	94	97	115	64	2.60	1.05	Satisfied
5	Newspapers	174	57	95	44	2.98	1.10	Satisfied
6	Journals	68	107	119	76	2.45	1.01	Not Satisfied
7	E-databases like Ebscohost, AGORA, JSTOR and BioOne,	69	118	115	68	2.51	1.00	Satisfied
8	Projects, thesis and dissertations	128	89	85	68	2.75	1.21	Satisfied
9	CD-ROM	119	92	91	68	2.71	1.11	Satisfied
10	Library staff	93	84	129	64	2.56	1.05	Satisfied

Source: Fieldwork 2025.

Table 3 above sought to find out the level of students satisfaction with the library resources provided. Result showed that, the respondents agreed to all the items except for journals which they disagreed scoring below the cut-off point of 2.50. This showed that the respondents are satisfied with some of the library resources provided.

Findings

1. The study found that library resources such as monographs/textbooks, card catalogue, online public access catalogue, e-books, newspapers, journals, e-databases such as AGORA, EBSCOhost, JSTOR etc, CD-ROM and library staff are provided by the polytechnic libraries.
2. The study also found that library resources have significant influence on academic performance of students in areas such as; improving their readings skills, helping them to pass their examination with high grades, making them participate in academic discourse among others.
3. The level of satisfaction from the library resources provided to the students was low.

Recommendations

1. The management of the Polytechnics Libraries should be more proactive in the area of awareness of information resources in the library by showing them the benefits they could derive from using them through various means including, flyers, user education programs need to be revolutionised, modern ICT equipment should be factor in, including practical instructions to ensure adequate understanding of library activities by users. By this, students will be well oriented about the activities of the library and how to access, retrieve and use the available information resources on their own effectively.
2. Constant display of newly acquired materials in the library and educating the students on how to identify, access and utilise the available information resources to achieve their educational goals
3. Library personnel should be made aware of the concepts and principles of modern marketing of library information resources and services. This can be performed through the holding of workshops, seminars, short-term courses, and other related programmes on the subject; regular staff training will help improve users' perception of the library staff and library services.

Conclusion

Polytechnic library is considered as a fundamental component and the heart beat of the polytechnic education. The centre provides information resources in accordance with the approved curriculum of all programmes undertaking in the polytechnic. This paper investigated library resources utilization on academic performance of students in public polytechnics in Benue State. The study affirmed that polytechnic libraries provide library resources to students. The studies also revealed that, the provision of library resources have positive effects on the students' academic performance even though students were not satisfied with some of the resources provided. Therefore, it is recommended that the management of the Polytechnics Libraries should be more proactive in the area of awareness of information resources in the library by showing them the benefits they could derive from using them through various means including, flyers, user education programs need to be revolutionised, modern ICT equipment should be factor in, including practical instructions to ensure adequate understanding of library activities by users. By this, students will be well oriented about the activities of the library and how to access, retrieve and use the available information resources on their own effectively.

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